

Prompts

The prompts were organized separately by question and category in which they were generated.

Question 1.a: Does the published SLR still address a current question (i.e., is the SLR current/actual in terms of its topic relevance for research and practice)?

1.a. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize encouraging comments that support the question "1.a Does the published RSL still address a topical issue (i.e., is the RSL current/real in terms of its topic's relevance to research and practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "Relevance as a key criterion for SE research"
- Participant P4: "No point in spending the resources in updating an SLR for a dead topic."
- Participant P7: "If the topic is no longer relevant there is limited need to update it (this could lead to less unnecessary reviews being undertaken)."
- Participant P10: "If the SLR address does not include the current questions than probably it will miss potential information regarding the area."
- Participant P12: "This should be a periodic check because SE practices and technologies evolves continuously"
- Participant P14: "otherwise no need to update"
- Participant P20: "It would not make sense to update an SLR if it addresses a question that is not of interest of the community anymore"
- Participant P23: "By addressing a current question, the updates for the answers are still valuable."
- Participant P24: "If "update" is meant strictly speaking, i.e. using the very same search approach, inclusion/exclusion criteria and RQs, then this question is relevant. If "update" has a more liberal definition, then this question is not as relevant, since the SLR's goal or context might be slightly different."
- Participant P25: "It is general question and can be related with SE SLRs"
- Participant P31: "There as an initial motivation for the SLR in the first place, which must still stand in my view. Otherwise, it is a waste of resources."
- Participant P32: "Software practice evolves constantly. It is important to determine if the previously conducted SLR captures the current state of practice. The same applies to software engineering research. The research methods and studies evolve and capturing the latest/current work is relevant for software engineering research."
- Participant P35: "Of course, because for instance in our SLR, out of about nine challenges identified, we were only able to address two major ones. While the remaining are open to both the researchers and practitioners."
- Participant P40: "If the topic is no longer relevant (perhaps because the problem has already been fixed) it is not worth updating the SLR"
- Participant P41: "What is the purpose of addressing no-relevant questions??"

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- Participant P42: "This question is extremely important. Maybe the question is not relevant anymore. However, what I've noticed is that sometimes, when trying to update an SLR, you end up discovering new open topics. But the original question is already answered and solved."
- Participant P48: "Obviously so."
- Participant P51: "If the topic is not relevant to both research and practice, IMHO there is no need to aggregate and synthesize additional evidence about the topic. But how does one determine if a topic is relevant or not? If more primary studies are being published on the topic, then is that enough to conclude its research relevance? Likewise, practical relevance would also not be easy to determine. Things vary from one context to the other."
- Participant P55: "This question is logically necessary but I doubt that --- given SLRs are generally broad and things don't become irrelevant that quickly --- the answer will be irrelevant that often. Perhaps assess relevance in a non-dichotomous fashion so you can do a CBA or opportunity cost analysis?"
- Participant P59: "There is no reason to update an SLR if its research question doesn't address a current issue anymore. An outdated research question could have not new publications with a greater impact, and a small amount of new data about the old question potentially will don't change previous results."
- Participant P60: "This question is very relevant as topics may still be under investigation by some researchers but have no significant impact for practice."
- Participant P62: "It can indicate the appropriateness of the topic and revealing the need of answering (or getting more answers... In fact, I get confuse with the idea of an SLR. Do you mean secondary studies, including SLRs or just pure SLR?)"
- Participant P65: "SLRs are a lot of work to do right, and thus emphasis should be placed on current or new questions."
- Participant P66: "If it is not relevant, then a new SLR with new questions, which addresses the current problems, is a better option."
- Participant P68: "This question enables to identify the evolution of a research topic. "
- Participant P71: "This is obviously relevant to check for an SLR if its needs upgradation or not. But question is "who will check it". The researcher who will update the SLR or any other researcher will critically evaluate anyone else's SLR. Also it will need further guidelines like what kind of data being presented in the SLR, the quantitative data in the SLR under study, might easily give a hint that upgradation of that SLR required. But for subjective data, I guess further research would be required to rule it out."

1.a. Criticism

Synthesize criticism comments that support the question "1.a Does the published RSL still address a topical issue (i.e., is the RSL current/real in terms of its topic's relevance to research and practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P30: "Some SLRs focus on research while others provide suggestions to improve practice. The topic should be relevant, but not necessarily for both contexts."
- Participant P46: "How do you (objectively) know if the question is still current without updating the SLR? You can rely on your "feeling" by looking at what happens in conferences, but this is just an adhoc

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solution. One way to address the question of relevance would be to conduct a SLR update..."

- Participant P49: "I'm not sure what would constitute a question that wasn't still current in the context of software engineering. Few systematic reviews (if any) in our field can be considered as being conclusive in any way. Also, we are probing at a 'science of the artificial' rather than the physical world, so we don't really have a fixed, physical context -- software engineering techniques and practices may well evolve, making it even less likely that any findings are anything like conclusive!"
- Participant P50: "Honestly, I am not sure what your questionnaire refers to. I first had to guess what SLR can stand for. I guess it is systematic literature review. "The published SLR" does not refer to my own SLR, but is a general question? This question is relevant, but it could make sense to update an SLR to show that the question is no longer relevant because no-one publishes about this topic any longer. This is interesting, too."
- Participant P53: "The way that this question is phrased sounds like it could be justified for evaluating work primarily on novelty - which imo is a big problem in SE research today because it forces young researchers to be more opportunistic than make lasting contributions. I would rephrase to something like "does this address an engineering problem in software?" - perhaps that captures the spirit of the question."

1.a. Suggestion

Synthesize suggestion comments that support the question "1.a Does the published RSL still address a topical issue (i.e., is the RSL current/real in terms of its topic's relevance to research and practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P12: "This should be a periodic check because SE practices and technologies evolves continuously"
- Participant P18: "This seems somewhat similar to asking whether a certain piece of research (e.g., an experiment reported in a primary study) is relevant or interesting. It may be subjective and depend on the reader/reviewer. How would we decide whether or not a question is current or not and whether a topic might be of interest for research and practice? To give an example, some practitioners argue that some of the original architectural patterns from the POSA book (Buschmann et al.) are "outdated" and not used anymore, while Stack Overflow still discusses many of these "outdated" patterns - who would decide whether architectural patterns are still current? If this question is included, some guidance would be useful."
- Participant P37: "Only providing two options is not enough. I would say all the questions should be relevant. However, the impact of each question is different (i.e., sth. is more important than others when considering to update an SLR)."
- Participant P52: "I believe it would be helpful to link this question to some objective criteria, e.g., 5 years have passed since the SLR was published, or new methods, applications, or concepts have emerged since then that justify an update. The field of CS is so dynamic that I believe that SLRs will become obsolete faster than in the health domain."
- Participant P53: "The way that this question is phrased sounds like it could be justified for evaluating work primarily on novelty - which

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imo is a big problem in SE research today because it forces young researchers to be more opportunistic than make lasting contributions. I would rephrase to something like "does this address an engineering problem in software?" - perhaps that captures the spirit of the question."

- Participant P55: "This question is logically necessary but I doubt that --- given SLRs are generally broad and things don't become irrelevant that quickly --- the answer will be irrelevant that often. Perhaps assess relevance in a non-dichotomous fashion so you can do a CBA or opportunity cost analysis?"

1.a. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "1.a Does the published RSL still address a topical issue (i.e., is the RSL current/real in terms of its topic's relevance to research and practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P5: "In general, you can summarize the subject and help to find good directions for new works."
- Participant P6: "Reviewing open source in estimating effort development."
- Participant P19: "SLR sometimes covers emerging research topics in which the research community did not engage to investigate. Consequently, you noted that researchers produced a reduced or an absent number of studies about such topics."
- Participant P24: "If "update" is meant strictly speaking, i.e. using the very same search approach, inclusion/exclusion criteria and RQs, then this question is relevant. If "update" has a more liberal definition, then this question is not as relevant, since the SLR's goal or context might be slightly different."
- Participant P28: "There is no globally accepted open source software process model."
- Participant P33: "If the SLR still addresses a current issue, it might not necessary to update it. In turn, if the field has evolved and moved on, the need for an update may be given."
- Participant P36: "I was unsure about this question. My initial thought was that it is relevant because it doesn't make sense to work on something that is not relevant. However, it depends on what you mean by "current/actual". It may be the case that it is a topic that is not super-relevant for industry but it is a foundation for the field and, therefore, it is still relevant."
- Participant P42: "This question is extremely important. Maybe the question is not relevant anymore. However, what I've noticed is that sometimes, when trying to update an SLR, you end up discovering new open topics. But the original question is already answered and solved."
- Participant P47: "continuity"
- Participant P50: "Honestly, I am not sure what your questionnaire refers to. I first had to guess what SLR can stand for. I guess it is systematic literature review. ""The published SLR"" does not refer to my own SLR, but is a general question? This question is relevant, but it could make sense to update an SLR to show that the question is no longer relevant because no-one publishes about this topic any longer. This is interesting, too."
- Participant P54: "The field of system of systems architecture has grown since this SLR, particularly software-intensive systems of systems."

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There is ongoing research in this area, and there have been subsequent SLRs that studied narrower areas of the field."

- Participant P63: "My published SLR relevant to my research"
- Participant P67: "The SLR addresses the links between maturity models, agility and web engineering. It is still a topic where discussions are happening as organizations still try to find a way to combine agility in operating with ensuring established processes for quality and repeatability"
- Participant P71: "This is obviously relevant to check for an SLR if its needs upgradation or not. But question is "who will check it". The researcher who will update the SLR or any other researcher will critically evaluate anyone else's SLR. Also it will need further guidelines like what kind of data being presented in the SLR, the quantitative data in the SLR under study, might easily give a hint that upgradation of that SLR required. But for subjective data, I guess further research would be required to rule it out."

Question 1.b: Has the SLR had good access or use (i.e., has the SLR had an impact on research and/or practice)?

1.b. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "1.b: Has the SLR had good access or use (i.e., has the SLR had an impact on research and/or practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "This is an indication on whether or not the SLR is relevant."
- Participant P5: "You also can join the relevant papers about the subject, it helps very much the researchers."
- Participant P7: "This shows the current SLR is of importance to the community."
- Participant P10: "This is relevant because the use of SLR in academia and industry is important. If there is no use or access than why to do an SLR even?"
- Participant P12: "Research without impact (short or long term) is pointless."
- Participant P20: "to update a SLR that has not good access or use might be losing time."
- Participant P25: "Yes, this question is also general in context and can be related with SE SLRs."
- Participant P35: "Absolutely yes, especially if the survey covers both research and practice."
- Participant P38: "Sure! It is a comprehensive collection of research findings in the area. Save a lot of time to view too many papers - just look into SLR published for a researcher to get good idea on the topic."
- Participant P42: "If the SLR didn't have an impact, maybe it's not worth it."
- Participant P47: "if by "good access" you mean high citation, then yes because citation is always considered one indicator of impact."
- Participant P49: "If the systematic review has triggered further research, then that is a good reason to update any findings. Not sure about we can assess whether it has had any impact on practice. Longer

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term I'd hope this would be a relevant factor, not so sure that it is at the moment."

- Participant P50: "If the study is not read and cited, it is no longer relevant. However, a similar study could attract more readers. I do not think that these two first questions should be yes-no-criteria."
- Participant P51: "I think the question is relevant. However, once again how to determine the impact on research and/or practice? I would like to highlight that citation count could be very misleading. We are aware that a large percentage of citations of an SLR might just be citations for the sake of it, i.e., they would not be true indicators of research/practice impact."
- Participant P56: "The question is relevant but I think a user of this framework will need some examples to assess impact. We recently used qualitative citation analysis to assess the impact of one of our highly cited SLRs and concluded as expected that the citing papers do not build on our work. <https://torkar.github.io/pdfs/sample-sigchi.pdf>."
- Participant P60: "SLR papers may be published once and fall into ostracism after a while due to their lack of systematism. Hence, their high/constant citations should be considered as a requirement for updating papers."
- Participant P65: "This is nice to have, but good user is hard to quantify. 5-10 citations could be an equally significant impact as 50-100 citations."
- Participant P66: "An update is only needed for an item which has enough significance."
- Participant P68: "This question is relevant to know the interest of the scientific community or practitioners on the research topic."

1.b. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "1.b: Has the SLR had good access or use (i.e., has the SLR had an impact on research and/or practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P3: "actually, I am not sure how much access relates to impact / relevance. Sometimes, people cite other studies (e.g., a tertiary study), which hides the original SLR's importance."
- Participant P18: "As before, this question is rather subjective. Measuring impact on practice in Software Engineering is difficult. Measuring impact on research based on citations may be misleading (e.g., maybe a SLR is quoted as a good/bad example, maybe the SLR is on a topic that is trendy at a certain point in time, what would be a "sufficient" number of citations [in particular when the SLR is on a niche topic], etc.)."
- Participant P19: "This point is important but does not justify an update of the SLR. The quantity of primary studies researchers produced about the research topic, and most importantly, new findings justify an update of the SLR. New impactful findings could imply future access or use of an SLR."
- Participant P23: "The previous version should not be a bias for the expectation for the update, it could be too limited or rejected to be published. Sometimes the lack of updates caused it to be rejected to be published or to be considered in practice."
- Participant P24: "Since an update might boost access or use, this question is not relevant. There might be a good reason behind an update that has nothing to do with access or use of the old SLR."

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- Participant P30: "Without a clear indicator of impact or usage, it is difficult to assess the value of this criterion. A SLR that addresses a popular topic can have more research impact (e.g., counting the number of cites) than others. In the case of industry relevance, or practice, I think that measuring its impact is difficult."
- Participant P31: "What is "good access" and "good use"? Also, awareness of some research topics might be perceived in different time periods and require some maturation."
- Participant P32: "If I understood the framework correctly, the SLR will not be updated if it doesn't have good citations for example (the analysis will not continue to Step 2). However, the SLR might not have good access or use because of many reasons such as the venue or quality of the SLR. The SLR may be published ahead of its time and the software committee and practice may not be fully aware of its importance. Or the problem addressed in the previous SLR is more relevant now than when it was published. In conclusion, "access and use" can be used as a supporting criterion however, it is not enough to not update an SLR only because it does not have good access or use."
- Participant P33: "Two issues here: First, it is hard to measure. Of course, we can count citations, but these citation are often due to reference a body of knowledge as part of a paper, so it is for me no real indicator of whether the SLR itself had good access. Second, beyond that, the access/usage is difficult to measure objectively."
- Participant P40: "Sometimes the very fact of not having had a significant impact makes it necessary to update the SLR (so that it does have that impact)."
- Participant P48: "Its impact is not necessarily coupled with its necessity or quality."
- Participant P51: "I think the is question is relevant. However, once again how to determine the impact on research and/or practice? I would like to highlight that citation count could be very misleading. We are aware that a large percentage of citations of an SLR might just be citations for the sake of it, i.e, they would not be true indicators of research/practice impact."
- Participant P52: "What is the definition of "good" access? I believe there should be a unified way to tell this bc the answer will vary greatly if the first SLR was publicly distributed or if it was hidden behind a paywall or in a local repository that is not indexed by search databases (e.g., university rep)."
- Participant P59: "The problem within this question is: what's good access or use? Older SLR tends to have a more significant impact and amount of citations. Still, there isn't a deterministic measure to certify that an SLR will obtain a certain number of citations after five years or more. Also, an SLR with a hundred citations could be less relevant in a field than another one with fifty citations in another context."
- Participant P61: "Answers to such a question is highly dependent on too many factors that will vary across domains and topics."
- Participant P62: "Not sure I got the idea of relevance here. It is always under the perspective of needing. For instance, an SLR can be of low impact but important for a specific context)."
- Participant P65: "This is nice to have, but good user is hard to quantify. 5-10 citations could be an equally significant impact as 50-100 citations."

1.b. Suggestion

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Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "1.b: Has the SLR had good access or use (i.e., has the SLR had an impact on research and/or practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P4: "If the original SLR had a negligible impact it may be the case that its insights are not that useful. But then, I guess it depends. It may be the case that new knowledge has surfaced since the original SLR (e.g. that a significant enough body of knowledge has emerged since the original one, justifying the update even if the original SLR was not so relevant.)"
- Participant P46: "Would however split the question. 1) Is the SLR accessible (not behind a paywall)? 2) Is it used (cited, by whom)?"
- Participant P50: "If the study is not read and cited, it is no longer relevant. However, a similar study could attract more readers. I do not think that these two first questions should be yes-no-criteria."
- Participant P52: "What is the definition of "good" access? I believe there should be a unified way to tell this bc the answer will vary greatly if the first SLR was publicly distributed or if it was hidden behind a paywall or in a local repository that is not indexed by search databases (e.g., university rep)."
- Participant P53: "The wording is awkward, I prefer the i.e. part to the first part."
- Participant P55: "Good access needs to be defined and time normalised? Maybe recent access?"
- Participant P56: "The question is relevant but I think a user of this framework will need some examples to assess impact. We recently used qualitative citation analysis to assess the impact of one of our highly cited SLRs and concluded as expected that the citing papers do not build on our work. <https://torkar.github.io/pdfs/sample-sigchi.pdf>"

1.b. Others

Synthesize "Others" comments that support the question "1.b: Has the SLR had good access or use (i.e., has the SLR had an impact on research and/or practice)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P6: "somehow."
- Participant P11: "Might be hard to judge, especially regarding practice as that might not be reported in literature."
- Participant P14: "Update still might be necessary/meaningful, if the SLR had no good access or use, but its an additional indication that the update would be worthwhile."
- Participant P28: "Our SLR was used in others SLRs and/or in related works."
- Participant P39: "But, relevant current topics (SLRs) may have been published at events/journals with little impact."
- Participant P43: "I am not sure we yet have a good way to measure this question in SE. I think the impact on practice would be more interesting, but harder to measure."
- Participant P54: "69 citations, according to Google Scholar."
- Participant P63: "Help to identify to research problems."
- Participant P67: "The document has been consistently cited since its publication."
- Participant P71: "aparently if an slr has not much citations, it seems its applicability is less in reserach or industry. The other aspect is

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poor quality of SLR, so here the conference or Journal that has published the SLR needs to be taken in to account."

Question 1.c: Has the SLR used valid methods and was it well conducted (i.e., has the SLR been carried out properly and using a sound methodology, e.g., with clear inclusion criteria and quality assessment)?

1.c. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "1.c. Has the SLR used valid methods and was it well conducted (i.e., has the SLR been carried out properly and using a sound methodology, e.g., with clear inclusion criteria and quality assessment)?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P4: "Otherwise, rather than an update, perhaps one should consider a better designed and conducted SLR."
- Participant P10: "This is relevant because if an SLR is not conducted using valid methods then there is potential threat to its replication and validity of results."
- Participant P18: "There is no point in updating a methodologically flawed study (assuming we would follow the same method)."
- Participant P20: "It is worth asking that. If the answer is YES, we might keep methods, otherwise we have to fix the problems and do the SLR again from scratch."
- Participant P23: "If the previous version was not well conducted, you should start a new review from scratch instead."
- Participant P24: "See 1a: If "update" is meant strictly speaking, i.e. using the very same search approach, inclusion/exclusion criteria and RQs, then this question is essential. Without a valid and reliable original, an update is meaningless. If "update" has a more liberal definition, meaning that the search approach, inclusion/exclusion criteria and RQs can be improved, the question is not relevant."
- Participant P25: "Yes, this question can be included."
- Participant P30: "A sound methodology increases the credibility of results."
- Participant P31: "Otherwise, why should one believe and use it?"
- Participant P33: "If not, I would wonder why it has been accepted initially. But of course, it is relevant that an SLR is conducted with care."
- Participant P40: "If the SLR was not executed properly then it is better to redo it, not update it."
- Participant P47: "there are a lot of published SLRs that are not methodologically sound, they should be ignored."
- Participant P48: "Updating a badly constructed SLR is a sunk cost fallacy."
- Participant P50: "Updating a badly made SLR makes no sense. Better to redesign a new study."
- Participant P60: "SLR design methodology should be considered once there is a possibility of updating it. Particularly, checklists could be helpful at this point. Making inclusion/exclusion criteria, data extraction protocols and tabulated files with extracted data should be made available as open artefacts."
- Participant P62: "It is crucial in any secondary study. Otherwise, replicability (or updating in this case) is challenge."

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- Participant P65: "An update must build on the reliability of the earlier work, unless the update is a do-over."
- Participant P66: "if the original criterion is faulty, update will carry the same faults. However, the terms like well conducted can be quite subjective."
- Participant P68: "This question is important to know the applied methodology, as well as the evaluation criteria used."

1.c. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "1.c. Has the SLR used valid methods and was it well conducted (i.e., has the SLR been carried out properly and using a sound methodology, e.g., with clear inclusion criteria and quality assessment)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P19: "In my opinion, possible shortcomings the researcher identifies in the study selection method can be a reason to justify an update of the SLR."
- Participant P32: "Depends. If the SLR update should follow the same methods as the previous SLR then it is not a good idea to use the same methods. However, it does not indicate that the update is not "needed". In my opinion, if an SLR has not been conducted rigorously then there is a need for another study. Particularly when using a more rigorous approach will generate different and more accurate results."
- Participant P36: "I believe in this case the update will require more effort because rather than an only updating the SLR, some re-do may be needed in order to achieve research rigor in the original study. However, I don't think this is a reason for not starting the work if the topic is really relevant."
- Participant P52: "If the answer to this question is "No", I believe that the original protocol should be amended."

1.c. Suggestion

Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "1.c. Has the SLR used valid methods and was it well conducted (i.e., has the SLR been carried out properly and using a sound methodology, e.g., with clear inclusion criteria and quality assessment)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P46: "Again, split into two questions if you mean two things (method description and execution). Otherwise rephrase to mean only one thing."
- Participant P53: "Those are two separate questions, I would separate them. Choosing a valid methodology is different than properly carrying it out. That can have an impact on editorial decisions, for example, maybe reviewers don't like a particular methodology (e.g. snowball sampling) but the editors are okay with it, then the paper doesn't get rejected for a single decision even though it was carried out just fine. But both questions are relevant."
- Participant P56: "In my opinion, a pointer to possible ways to assess SLR quality will be handy for the user of the framework - see for example <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584919300771>"

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- Participant P71: "This can be easily checked by checking the SLR against the methodologies of SLR."

1.c. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "1.c. Has the SLR used valid methods and was it well conducted (i.e., has the SLR been carried out properly and using a sound methodology, e.g., with clear inclusion criteria and quality assessment)?" Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "This is relevant, but must be balanced with a synthesis and interpretation of the outcomes. Only classifying studies is a limited contribution."
- Participant P6: "conducted using the framework."
- Participant P7: "If there was an initial review that was not sound, that doesn't mean an update isn't required - it might mean a full new review should be conducted. I think this is relevant but I would argue that if the answer was no to the original being well carried out it shouldn't have made it through the publishing process. That said, views on what is meant by "carried out correctly" may change over time, the SLR may have slipped past reviewers, or been part of a non-peer reviewed process."
- Participant P12: "Research validity threats should be eliminated in the future studies if possible (continuous improvement)."
- Participant P14: "should not have been published, if not, but unfortunately, I know, this is not a given."
- Participant P24: "See 1a: If "update" is meant strictly speaking, i.e. using the very same search approach, inclusion/exclusion criteria and RQs, then this question is essential. Without a valid and reliable original, an update is meaningless. If "update" has a more liberal definition, meaning that the search approach, inclusion/exclusion criteria and RQs can be improved, the question is not relevant."
- Participant P28: "Our method was valid but we don't perform a quality assessment."
- Participant P35: "I can say yes, because most of the SLR papers we have come across used valid methods/procedures."
- Participant P37: "The three questions seem to be to some extent overlapped. As an example, is it possible that the lack of use of an SLR is because that the SLR doesn't address any current question?"
- Participant P38: "Just that there exist some papers that claimed to use SLR methods did not fully follow the SLR protocols."
- Participant P42: "If the SLR wasn't well conducted, maybe you could conduct one properly. If it was well conducted, I'd say that updating it is going to depend on how long ago the SLR was conducted."
- Participant P49: "One of the concerns we had from our recent tertiary study assessing the usefulness of findings from systematic reviews for teaching and practice was that many were not conducted or reported well. Even when quality assessments were performed, they were not used to inform the later stages. And many reviews used fairly weak forms of aggregation/synthesis (such as narrative synthesis). There may be various reasons for this (I suspect many were led by PhD students who were understandably more challenged when it came to synthesis). In some cases, where the findings look promising, this might be a very good reason to repeat or extend a systematic review in software engineering. Might be a problem getting it funded of course!"

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- Participant P54: "Followed standard guidelines (Kitchenham and Charters). Checked sensitivity of search using a standard set of primary studies."
- Participant P55: "In terms of decision making you could argue that if the methods are poor then there's more need for an update/replacement?"
- Participant P59: "The notion of what is a valid method and how to conduct a research changer over time."
- Participant P63: "because we used Standard methodology of SLR."
- Participant P67: "The document is based in a systematic approach to literature review and has followed a sound methodology."

Decision Driver 1: DD1. Would you agree that ALL questions in Step 1 MUST have a "YES" answer, before moving on to Step 2, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 1 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?

DD1. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "DD1. Would you agree that ALL questions in Step 1 MUST have a "YES" answer, before moving on to Step 2, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 1 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P12: "If the update idea is to use exactly the same method and questions then I agree with this. However, I don't see any reason to do some things differently in the new SLR if they improve some aspect in research reliability, validity, novelty etc."
- Participant P31: "In particular, I think the order they are asked is also important. In fact, I would perfectly understand aborting if the answer to Step 1. a) is "No"."

DD1. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "DD1. Would you agree that ALL questions in Step 1 MUST have a "YES" answer, before moving on to Step 2, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 1 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "I am afraid of such rigid guidelines, because they may prevent novelty."
- Participant P4: "In general, my answer would be yes, but there is the caveat I noted on question 1.b: it may be the case that the original SLR was performed "too early" and so was conducted on a not solid enough body of knowledge. So, it may be the case that a relevant number of relevant primary studies has emerged since that would make the update justifiable. So, I think this is more complicated than a simple yes or no. It depends."
- Participant P7: "Regarding Q1.c - If there was an initial review that was not sound, that doesn't mean an update isn't required - it might mean a full new review should be conducted. I think this is relevant but I would argue that if the answer was no to the original being well carried out it shouldn't have made it through the publishing process."

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That said, views on what is meant by "carried out correctly" may change over time, the SLR may have slipped past reviewers, or been part of a non-peer reviewed process. (response copied from earlier question)."

- Participant P11: "Sometimes good papers simply get overlooked for various reasons so the "popularity" criteria (b) is not as strong as (a) and (c) which are crucial."
- Participant P14: "a and c should be YES, b I would see as optional."
- Participant P17: "YES on all three questions does not cover situations where there has been exponential publications growth on a specific topic, a shift in the terminology related to the topic (affecting the automated search through keywords), or major technological innovations that put the results into new light since the previous SLR."
- Participant P23: "I sincerely believe that the framework is way too simple, including step 1. There are many other intrinsic details that the researchers behind the review may have learned by reviewing the primary studies. This knowledge should be considered much more than those simple shallow questions."
- Participant P24: "Again, this comes down to the definition of update. However, even with a strict definition of update, I could imagine valid reasons for an update even when 1b is answered No."
- Participant P25: "Questions 1.a and 1.c seem related, if both or either one is answered 'Yes' then decision model must proceed towards STEP 2. Where Question 1.b gives looks redundant, according to my understanding 1.a has already asked about SLR's RQ impact and practice, if they needed to be revised then 1.b will be automatically achieved."
- Participant P29: "I agree that upgrading a high-impact SLR is more interesting, but I think those that didn't have this access level could also be upgraded. Maybe the updated SLR does have a better impact, or maybe even the topic covered will become relevant in the future."
- Participant P33: "As mentioned, for the question about usage/good access, I find it hard to measure. Also, a rather low access does not necessarily imply that the SLR is useless. So, I do not think that this question must be answered with yes to proceed."
- Participant P40: "Sometimes the very fact of not having had a significant impact makes it necessary to update the SLR (so that it does have that impact)."
- Participant P48: "A 2 out of 3 majority would be enough in my view."
- Participant P49: "I would follow up my point about the third criterion. If it was felt that the topic could offer value, but the conduct looked as though it was flawed (including the synthesis), I think this would be a motive for updating in SE."
- Participant P50: "As written above, if the research question is no longer relevant, the SLR update can show that it is so. If the study has not been cited, one should think about why."
- Participant P52: "I believe that 1.c. should be a reason to consider amending the protocol of an SLR. I agree that a new protocol does characterize a NEW SLR, but I think it is important to preserve the history link with research that came before. Besides, it would be nice to compare if the new protocol retrieved the same body of work and how the analysis derived from it is different (preferably richer in terms of breadth and/or depth)."
- Participant P55: "Replacing/updating a poor SLR is more important because the findings are untrustworthy."
- Participant P56: "I think it cannot be a strict rule as stated in the original framework. I am mainly concerned about the answer to 1b as it may be a timing issues, visibility due to the venue, sometimes unfortunately who is the author may also influence the readership and impact of a work. So, in case the answer is no for any of the questions,

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the author should have presented a strong motivation to still justify a need for an update."

- Participant P59: "Taking into consideration the question about the method validity, even when a method is not valid, or the research isn't well-conducted. However, the problem still relevant; an SRL could deserve an update."
- Participant P61: "Answers to question 1c is highly dependent on too many factors that will vary across domains and topics. And the research field may have been just emerging and evolved slowly, while suddenly with an emergency makes it become highly relevant even if it had had little impact in the previous years."
- Participant P62: "As I have said, the idea of impact is not clear to me. I would not suggest that something not presenting a sort of relevance (regardless the counting metric) in some past moment could not raise the interest in the current moment."
- Participant P71: "I have answered 1b, it does not seem relevant to me."

DD1. Suggestion

Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "DD1. Would you agree that ALL questions in Step 1 MUST have a "YES" answer, before moving on to Step 2, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 1 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P4: "In general, my answer would be yes, but there is the caveat I noted on question 1.b: it may be the case that the original SLR was performed "too early" and so was conducted on a not solid enough body of knowledge. So, it may be the case that a relevant number of relevant primary studies has emerged since that would make the update justifiable. So, I think this is more complicated than a simple yes or no. It depends."
- Participant P11: "Sometimes good papers simply get overlooked for various reasons so the "popularity" criteria (b) is not as strong as (a) and (c) which are crucial."
- Participant P14: "a and c should be YES, b I would see as optional."
- Participant P25: "Questions 1.a and 1.c seem related, if both or either one is answered 'Yes' then decision model must proceed towards STEP 2. Where Question 1.b gives looks redundant, according to my understanding 1.a has already asked about SLR's RQ impact and practice, if they needed to be revised then 1.b will be automatically achieved."
- Participant P30: "For question 1.a, I would prefer a wording like "research and/or practice". Concerning question 1.b, I would like more information about potential indicators to measure relevance in both research and practice."
- Participant P37: "Besides the aforementioned things, how about research questions? Or do research questions belong to Q1? How about the year of publication? If an SLR was published in last year. Is it necessary to conduct an update? I think you should first clarify the meaning of ""update an SLR"" in the beginning of this questionnaire. What exactly does it mean? For example, does re-design the SLR belongs to update? If the original SLR has for example three research questions, while I kept the first two and redesigned third one. Would that be update?"
- Participant P48: "A 2 out of 3 majority would be enough in my view."

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- Participant P66: "Question 3 can be made more specific. Is it not really tough to judge the validation of an already published work ??"

DD1. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "DD1. Would you agree that ALL questions in Step 1 MUST have a "YES" answer, before moving on to Step 2, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 1 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P10: "The steps does not seem overlapping and can followed individually."
- Participant P12: "If the update idea is to use exactly the same method and questions then I agree with this. However I don't see any reason to do some things differently in the new SLR if they improve some aspect in research reliability, validity, novelty etc."
- Participant P18: "See comments above."
- Participant P21: "If we are forcing to the participant for choosing yes, then how it could be fair response. In my opinion it should not."
- Participant P32: "As I only mentioned one question as relevant the answer is "Yes" to this question. Although I would like to point out that the other question are not completely irrelevant. Probably instead of an exclusion based on yes and no answers, weights could be assigned to each question. Some sort of scoring will allow more flexibility."
- Participant P37: "Besides the aforementioned things, how about research questions? Or do research questions belong to Q1? How about the year of publication? If an SLR was published in last year. Is it necessary to conduct an update? I think you should first clarify the meaning of ""update an SLR"" in the beginning of this questionnaire. What exactly does it mean? For example, does re-design the SLR belongs to update? If the original SLR has for example three research questions, while I kept the first two and redesigned third one. Would that be update?"
- Participant P58: "I have assumed that we are talking about extending (updating) an EXISTING SLR, not creating a new one. I think this is not very clear from the questions (should there have been an introduction about the context here?)"
- Participant P65: "See my second comment above."

Question 2.a: Are there any new relevant methods (examples of new methods can be new ways to search for evidence and to do the synthesis of evidence, inclusion of other types of study designs, new statistical techniques or improvements to existing techniques?

2.a. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "2.a: Are there any new relevant methods (examples of new methods can be new ways to search for evidence and to do the synthesis of evidence, inclusion of other types of study designs, new statistical techniques or improvements to existing techniques?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "Always keep an eye for the novelty."

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- Participant P4: "Might bring a new perspective on the subject, previously unexplored."
- Participant P7: "If there are, a new review would be justified. "
- Participant P10: "This is relevant because the evidence needs are correct justification. If the results are proven wrongly than the reader will be misguided."
- Participant P12: "I don't see any reason to stick with old/outdated methods."
- Participant P14: "new results can be achieved/derived then."
- Participant P24: "This question is more important than either of 1 a-c."
- Participant P25: "yes, it is relevant."
- Participant P30: "New methods to search evidence can identify relevant primary papers that were not found in a previous SLR. Indeed, analysis and synthesis methods can refine previous SLR results."
- Participant P31: "This could affect the analysis results and thus the implications."
- Participant P33: "Finding new way/methods to adress a topic or even extend the body of knowledge is always a relevant aspect."
- Participant P42: "With new methods, you might find new evidence. Crossing information that you haven't done previously may bring up to light different findings."
- Participant P47: "new methods should always be considered if an arguments is being formed for an update to an existing SLR."
- Participant P59: "It's essential to reflect if the method utilized still fit in the research question."
- Participant P60: "The creation of novel research methods should considered as a criteria for updating SLRs. These novel methods build upon the state of the art of a given area and may overcome the existing ones."
- Participant P65: "SLRs shouldn't be locked into methods of the past are deemed less reliable in the present."
- Participant P68: "This question is important to know the applied methodology, and the results generated by them. In addition, how such methodologies have strengthened over the years."

2.a. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "2.a: Are there any new relevant methods (examples of new methods can be new ways to search for evidence and to do the synthesis of evidence, inclusion of other types of study designs, new statistical techniques or improvements to existing techniques?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P19: "New statistical techniques and new ways to synthesize the data could justify an update only if a new trend of tools and methods emerged and can improve the analysis significantly."
- Participant P45: "I am not sure what methods are meant. Methods for the SLR? Then it is not relevant."
- Participant P71: "I think new ways do not affect the findings directly. So it does not seem relevent to me."

2.a. Suggestion

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Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "2.a: Are there any new relevant methods (examples of new methods can be new ways to search for evidence and to do the synthesis of evidence, inclusion of other types of study designs, new statistical techniques or improvements to existing techniques?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P55: "I'd reframe to say are there relevant methods that weren't employed. It hardly matters if they are new or old."

2.a. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "2.a: Are there any new relevant methods (examples of new methods can be new ways to search for evidence and to do the synthesis of evidence, inclusion of other types of study designs, new statistical techniques or improvements to existing techniques?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P20: "in fact, at first I didn't understand the above question. I thought that you were asking the author of the updated SLR whether or not he has used new methods during the update. After advancing to the other questions in this group I understood that you are referring to the results of the update and I consider this a relevant question."
- Participant P23: "I only selected "No" to force you to review my answer. Sometimes you do not know the answer to the question prior to the update, therefore this question is often impractical."
- Participant P24: "This question is more important than either of 1 a-c."
- Participant P32: "Relevant if using the new relevant methods will produce new and useful results."
- Participant P35: "I think there should be, if the research involves practice then the input from the practitioners is very vital in getting better results."
- Participant P36: "I answered that it is relevant because I can imagine the case where a SLR is updated from a research method point of view. However, in practice, I have not seen such kind of studies in our field."
- Participant P37: "Are the methods regarding conducting the SLR itself, instead of methods regarding research topics? If Yes, then I would say it is less relevant (or not relevant)."
- Participant P45: "I am not sure what methods are meant. Methods for the SLR? Then it is not relevant."
- Participant P48: "Relevant but not necessarily applicable."
- Participant P49: "We should play down meta-analysis. There are very few of these in SE, and we did observe in our tertiary study that many useful reviews were largely based on primary studies that were some form of case study (how that term was interpreted is open to question). As previously, I think some would benefit more from better synthesis than from new studies, particularly if this took into account different forms of primary study."
- Participant P52: "I believe that this questions is related to the and/or aspect of my previous answer, i.e., that we should redo an SLR only if we can improve its depth and/or breadth. That being said, this question is related to the "breadth" side of this objective."
- Participant P54: "Clustering of evidence."

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- Participant P62: "NOT sure meta-analysis should be the target. It is quite hard to guarantee it can be possible in SE. New methods, such as Structured Synthesis can combine qualitative and quantitative evidence very well. It seems more realistic for SE."

Question 2.b: Are there any new studies, or other information (e.g., grey literature papers, in case such types of studies are also being considered for inclusion)?

2.b. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "2.b. Are there any new studies, or other information (e.g., grey literature papers, in case such types of studies are also being considered for inclusion)?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "As I understand it, this is the key motivation for updating SLRs."
- Participant P4: "This would be among if not the top motivation for updating an SLR."
- Participant P10: "This is highly relevant to bridge the gap between academia and industry in SLRs."
- Participant P12: "Yeah, I tend to agree but I would be very cautious about grey literature's value."
- Participant P14: "to include new information is the key purpose of the update isn't it?"
- Participant P19: "This is the most relevant aspect, but discarding the grey literature papers. In my opinion, SLR should give priority to analyze peer-reviewed studies. A systematic study that counts grey literature papers makes part of grey literature practically."
- Participant P24: "This question is more important than either of 1 a-c."
- Participant P30: "New studies can provide insights in particular contexts."
- Participant P31: "This could affect the analysis results and thus the implications."
- Participant P32: "Relevant however, depends on the number of new studies."
- Participant P33: "If the state of the art evolved, it is an important threat to an existing SLR (i.e., may require an update). So, absolutely relevant."
- Participant P36: "I think this is the most important reason to update a SLR."
- Participant P47: "If there are no new studies, what is the point of update to SLR?"
- Participant P52: "I don't see the point of redoing a SLR if zero new studies would be included."
- Participant P60: "Whenever a grey literature is made available by means of open repositories (e.g., with DOIs), they should be considered for inclusion."

2.b. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "2.b. Are there any new studies, or other information (e.g., grey literature papers, in case such types of studies are also being considered for inclusion)?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

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- Participant P35: "I think the study selection criteria should be based on a peer-reviewed and scientific paper rather than grey literature papers."
- Participant P59: "The researcher will find new studies just when performing the SLR update."

2.b. Suggestion

Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "2.b. Are there any new studies, or other information (e.g., grey literature papers, in case such types of studies are also being considered for inclusion)?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P71: "if there are a considerable amount of new studies been reported, then the SLR needs to be upgraded."

2.b. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "2.b. Are there any new studies, or other information (e.g., grey literature papers, in case such types of studies are also being considered for inclusion)?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P18: "It may be difficult to know whether there are new studies or new information *before* conducting an initial search for the SLR. Also, what would be the threshold for number of new studies?"
- Participant P20: "it is important to know the results of the update in terms of new studies or information."
- Participant P23: "It is often easy to probe for new related studies prior to updates, however, like I wrote earlier, it is not a strong evidence that there are new methods."
- Participant P24: "This question is more important than either of 1 a-c."
- Participant P32: "Relevant however, depends on the number of new studies."
- Participant P35: "I think the study selection criteria should be based on a peer-reviewed and scientific paper rather than grey literature papers."
- Participant P37: "Doesn't 2.b. contain 2.a.? Normally an SLR doesn't include grey literature, i.e., all methods are proposed and described in peer-reviewed and published studies."
- Participant P38: "I think white papers from SE industry can also be included in SLR - these are actual implementation in industry reported, and can be relevant to SLR."
- Participant P48: "Sufficient but not necessary condition (e.g. if 2.a is true)."
- Participant P49: "I think this is relevant, but I do wonder whether we have a much larger grey literature than clinical medicine. I know some researchers have tried to use the grey literature, but its diversity is an issue."
- Participant P50: "If the SLR does not contain later developments, it will be of less use for other researchers."
- Participant P54: "As noted above, this is an area of active research, and new studies have been published since this SLR."

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- Participant P55: "Though how does one know with out doing a new search?"
- Participant P56: "I am a bit wary of the very loose definition of grey literature as used by our colleagues promoting the use of multivocal literature reviews. Blogs and tweets are not grey literature in my opinion. I hope that you would define the bounds of grey literature to help the users of the framework."
- Participant P62: "I am answering with the perspective of empirical studies in technical literature. Not sure grey literature should be used in this case."
- Participant P65: "I dont understand this question."
- Participant P68: "The generation of new studies occurs in short periods of time. Thus, it can be said that there is a high probability that some studies will be published while conducting a review of the literature being conducted."
-

Decision Driver 2: Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 2 MUST have a "YES" answer before moving on to Step 3, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 2 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?

DD2. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "DD2. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 2 MUST have a "YES" answer before moving on to Step 3, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 2 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "Why else consider an update?"
- Participant P18: "Many New studies could justify an update, even if there are no new methods (and vice versa)."
- Participant P49: "Yes, I would agree with that."

DD2. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "DD2. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 2 MUST have a "YES" answer before moving on to Step 3, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 2 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P52: "I believe BOTH questions need to be true. Even if you are only changing the synthesis method (that can potentially impact your conclusions), investing your time and resources in an update that is assessing the exact same body of work seems wasteful."
- Participant P55: "I think the framework over-simplifies the situation."

DD2. Suggestion

Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "DD2. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 2 MUST have a "YES" answer

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before moving on to Step 3, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 2 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P24: "I would rather start the questioning with 2a and 2b, since 1a-c might prematurely exclude SLRs from an update although 2a or 2b give good reasons for it."
- Participant P31: "In particular, I think the questions are orthogonal so the current order is accidental. Maybe they could be asked in parallel."
- Participant P56: "For 2b, there should be additional argumentation about the amount of new literature, and why we expect the results to have changed since the last review."
- Participant P62: "However, it is necessary to evaluate the balancing between both. Effort could not worth considering the new level of confidence (due to an alternative method) or availability of new evidence (more of the same not sure is necessary)."

DD2. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "DD2. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 2 MUST have a "YES" answer before moving on to Step 3, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 2 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P23: "Only because of the latter."
- Participant P32: "Yes, however depends if the use of new methods will result in new findings. A reasonable assumption is required."
- Participant P48: "Agreed in principle, but it is more nuanced than that (it feels like a more conditional approach is required to avoid iterating over the same set of papers infinitely)."

Question 3.a: Will the adoption of new methods change the findings/conclusions or credibility?

3.a. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "3.a. Will the adoption of new methods change the findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P3: "The question is relevant to answer, but there may still be value in an updated SLR even if nothing changes (neither findings nor credibility)."
- Participant P4: "This would be a good reason for conducting it."
- Participant P12: "Makes sense. If the update makes finding less credible then I don't know why it could be published."
- Participant P14: "if yes, the update had a big impact, bot just adding more info along the same results."
- Participant P20: "One of the reasons of updating a SLR is because we know the state of the art has advanced and we want to see the effects on the previous SLR."

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- Participant P31: "This is crucial for assessing the SLR's update impact."
- Participant P32: "This is important. If the new methods do not change the findings/conclusions then it doesn't make sense to update the SLR."
- Participant P33: "IF this is the case, the whole updated SLR sheds new light on the topic. So, relevant."
- Participant P36: "This question is relevant for SLRs. Perhaps it is not so relevant for SMSs."
- Participant P47: "because if it does not make any changes to the already published findings what is the point of doing it again."
- Participant P48: "Obvious"
- Participant P60: "The inclusion of other statistical analysis techniques (e.g., effect size) can show that some techniques may not be actually as powerful as we thought before."

3.a. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "3.a. Will the adoption of new methods change the findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P3: "The question is relevant to answer, but there may still be value in an updated SLR even if nothing changes (neither findings nor credibility)."
- Participant P19: "New methods will be relevant only if the adoption of new ones changes the findings/conclusions to the correct side and not to the wrong one."
- Participant P23: "How can we surely know that? How do you wish to assess a review based on new methods without studies or data? Only the next question is relevant."
- Participant P35: "I don't think so, because updating may rather improve the quality of findings."
- Participant P51: "Adding a new method may or may not change the findings/conclusions. I understand that. However, adding a new method can be argued to have a positive impact on credibility. Or? Using an additional search method increases the credibility of the search process. It may or may not lead to additional studies or eventually may or may not change the findings. Thus, IMHO adoption of new (relevant) methods, regardless of their impact on findings/conclusions, potentially adds to the credibility of the SLR."
- Participant P52: "I did not follow this question. Change can be positive and negative. Should we not update an SLR if our new methods will increase its credibility?"
- Participant P59: "This question forces the researcher to infer a result before even perform the SLR update. The findings, conclusions, and credibility shouldn't have the content desired in the research planning phase."
- Participant P62: "IT is quite hard to consider it. To use new methods is fine and try it in previous secondary studies is fine and desired. However, it is quite hard to realize whether the new method can change the findings."
- Participant P68: "Depends on the reliability of the methodology."

3.a. Suggestion

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Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "3.a. Will the adoption of new methods change the findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P18: "This question is relevant, but more from an analysis perspective. Even if new methods do not change findings/conclusions, they could confirm previous findings and make an update to the SLR useful. In other words, the answer to this question does not need to be "Yes" in all cases."
- Participant P71: "If something directly affecting the findings/results then it should be taken in to account. But these new methods should have a research support i.e. these methods should have been already empirically evaluated on some SLRs to be considered."

3.a. Others

Synthesize "Others" comments that support the question "3.a. Will the adoption of new methods change the findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "This is about the synthesized assessment of the SLR."
- Participant P10: "Possible"
- Participant P21: "Perhaps"
- Participant P24: "An update seems very sensible in this case since there might be substantial "ripple effects"."
- Participant P30: "Several SLRs lacks of quality assessment of primary papers. Thus, assessing the quality of primary studies contributes to understand the extent results are derived from sound empirical research. Besides, SLRs can provide an assessment of the strength of the evidence to support reader to make decision about the relevance of conclusions."
- Participant P36: "This question is relevant for SLRs. Perhaps it is not so relevant for SMSs."
- Participant P37: "If you mean the methods of conducting an SLR, I would say it's less relevant. As an example, we are still using Grounded Theory (published in 1967) for qualitative data analysis. Would this happen a lot in reality? I think the most important thing should be the data itself instead of how we present the data."
- Participant P46: "While relevant, how can this be judged with confidence?"
- Participant P49: "I suspect that we might do better at improving credibility than improving the conclusions. Many of our systematic reviews are aggregating a much more mixed set of primary studies than would be the case in clinical medicine, so that may put a bound upon the likely extent for any 'improvements' in the findings. However, both are good reasons for updating a review."
- Participant P54: "This is a ridiculous question. You cannot know whether the findings and conclusions will change until you conduct the study. I'm answering yes anyway."
- Participant P55: "It's not just the methods but how well they're deployed and their impact in the context. This may be hard to anticipate."
- Participant P65: "Variations in study design and their impact on outcomes always deserve explanation."

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- Participant P70: "Well if the adoption of new methods really changes the credibility, then Yes the question is relevant. But how does a method change the credibility? This I am not sure."

Question 3.b: Will the inclusion of new data/studies/information change findings/conclusions or credibility?

3.b. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "3.b. Will the inclusion of new data/studies/information change findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P4: "Having reasons to suspect these findings/conclusions/credibility might change is an excellent reason for conducting the review. Nevertheless, it may not be mandatory. Even if the new data/studies/information does not affect the findings or conclusions, it might at least increase the credibility of results, or reinforce our confidence that old results still apply (e.g. consider an SLR conducted 10 years ago, on a topic for which there are now many more primary studies available than 10 years ago. Increasing the credibility of the results and supporting that old conclusions still apply may be useful by itself.)."
- Participant P10: "Yes"
- Participant P12: "Yeah, hopefully at least something changes."
- Participant P13: "There is always the risk that by including new studies/evidence, previous findings change. But isn't the point of SLR to summarize the current evidence? The existence of new evidence is already one reason for an update."
- Participant P14: "if yes, the update had a big impact, but just adding more info along the same results."
- Participant P19: "In my opinion, this aspect is the most important and is the definitive criteria for updating an SLR."
- Participant P20: "Same as previous question, we update an SLR to see the effect of new data/studies/information on our previous findings/conclusions."
- Participant P23: "More studies and data increase the statistical power, then yes."
- Participant P30: "The inclusion of new studies can address identified research gaps in a previous SLR. In addition, new studies can provide contextual factors that influence or change previous findings."
- Participant P31: "This is crucial for assessing the SLR's update impact."
- Participant P47: "this is no brainer, of course, why not?"
- Participant P48: "Also obvious."
- Participant P49: "This has to be a relevant question in any field, although I'm not sure how easy it would be to assess the likely effects of new data/studies. I could see how the medics could do this if there were new and interesting RCTs, but our primary studies are more mixed in form and quality."
- Participant P60: "New data/studies/information may provide more challenging scenarios to existing techniques and show that these techniques may not work well in every case."
- Participant P68: "The inclusion of new studies may change the results of a review (i.e., findings, contributions, challenges, and

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conclusions). We can take new directions, and provide different conclusions."

3.a. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "3.b. Will the inclusion of new data/studies/information change findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P35: "I still don't believe in that, but rather believed that it might increase the quality of findings."
- Participant P52: "I believe that the research should be done regardless if the answer to this question is "No", i.e., that the conclusions may remain the same. If there are sufficient new studies to justify an update of the SLR and the conclusions that we draw are still the same, we are making our conclusions stronger, which does not hurt!"
- Participant P59: "This question can only be fully answered after data analysis."

3.b. Suggestion

Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "3.b. Will the inclusion of new data/studies/information change findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P71: "If something directly affecting the findings/results then it should be taken in to account."

3.b. Others

Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "3.b. Will the inclusion of new data/studies/information change findings/conclusions or credibility?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "This is about the synthesised assessment of the SLR."
- Participant P3: "Same as above: The question is relevant to answer, but there may still be value in an updated SLR even if nothing changes (neither findings nor credibility)."
- Participant P4: "Having reasons to suspect these findings/conclusions/credibility might change is an excellent reason for conducting the review. Nevertheless, it may not be mandatory. Even if the new data/studies/information does not affect the findings or conclusions, it might at least increase the credibility of results, or reinforce our confidence that old results still apply (e.g. consider an SLR conducted 10 years ago, on a topic for which there are now many more primary studies available than 10 years ago. Increasing the credibility of the results and supporting that old conclusions still apply may be useful by itself.)"
- Participant P18: "This question is relevant, but more from an analysis perspective. Even if new data and studies do not change findings/conclusions, they could confirm previous findings and make an update to the SLR useful. In other words, the answer to this question does not need to be "Yes" in all cases."

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- Participant P21: "Perhaps."
- Participant P24: "An update seems very sensible in this case since there might be substantial "ripple effects"."
- Participant P32: "Same answer as 3.a."
- Participant P33: "Same as before."
- Participant P36: "Same comment than in previous question."
- Participant P46: "While relevant, how can this be judged with confidence?"
- Participant P49: "This has to be a relevant question in any field, although I'm not sure how easy it would be to assess the likely effects of new data/studies. I could see how the medics could do this if there were new and interesting RCTs, but our primary studies are more mixed in form and quality."
- Participant P54: "The field is maturing."
- Participant P55: "But how would one know in advance?"
- Participant P56: "Ok, you have it here - I raised this concern in step 2."
- Participant P62: "It seems similar on having more studies (previous step)."
- Participant P65: "Same as last justification."

Decision Driver 3: Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 3 MUST have a "YES" answer, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 3 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?

DD3. Encouraging Comment

Synthesize Encouraging comments that support the question "DD3. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 3 MUST have a "YES" answer, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 3 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P7: "There needs to be justification for the update, and these questions provide that."
- Participant P24: "Again Q 3a and b seem more important than 1a-c."
- Participant P31: "Either is crucial for assessing the SLR's update impact."
- Participant P58: "A bit strange questions, although relevant. Sometimes you will not know whether more studies will change the conclusion when planning/deciding on whether doing an update or not. What is here a change in conclusion? Is even stronger evidence in favor of a relationship a change in conclusion? Updating a SLR that strengthen the previous finding may be worthwhile. PS: In the original decision framework there is a "maybe". I think that maybe makes meaning."
- Participant P68: "I believe these questions can guide future updates."

DD3. Criticism

Synthesize Criticism comments that support the question "DD3. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 3 MUST have a "YES" answer, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 3 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you

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do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P1: "The credibility could be sufficient before, but the update could be to refresh it - which of course might be judged as a more credible SLR."
- Participant P3: "There may be value in providing an update even if there is no new insight. The updated SLR may answer the question whether new methods / studies change previous insights, and the answer may be "no" - and this is perfectly valid."
- Participant P18: "The answer to both questions could be "No" in my opinion. New methods and new studies/data could confirm the findings from previous reviews. New insights would probably make the SLR more interesting to the reader though, but that might be another issue."
- Participant P44: "I didn't find any relevant questions."
- Participant P50: "It is possible that there is new research in the field that needs to be included, without changing the conclusions."
- Participant P51: "It can not be judged in advance with certainty if the new methods or additional data/studies would change the findings or not. It also depends on the scale (number of new primary studies added as a result of additional data/information or new methods) if you can estimate the likely impact on the findings/conclusions. 2. If the update increases the sample size (of primary studies) from N1 to N2 without any impact on the findings/conclusions, wouldn't that also be a contribution in a way that now the conclusions are based on N2 number of studies, instead of N1. 3. Lastly, In Step 3 two different aspects are ORed together, i.e., findings/conclusions and credibility. It is possible to argue for the increase in credibility just because new methods are used and/or more studies/data are identified."
- Participant P52: "My perception is that we may not need Step 3 at all, i.e., all we need to know in order to make a decision is covered in Steps 1 and 2. But, depending on how you frame question 3.a, step 3 might be needed."
- Participant P59: "There aren't relevant questions in this section."
- Participant P66: "Sometimes inclusion of new data or methods may have enough significance although the overall conclusion is same."

DD3. Suggestion

Synthesize Suggestion comments that support the question "DD3. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 3 MUST have a "YES" answer, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 3 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P52: "My perception is that we may not need Step 3 at all, i.e., all we need to know in order to make a decision is covered in Steps 1 and 2. But, depending on how you frame question 3.a, step 3 might be needed."
- Participant P54: "Question 3.a. should be reworked - see my comment above."

DD3. Others

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Synthesize "others" comments that support the question "DD3. Would you agree that AT LEAST ONE of the questions in Step 3 MUST have a "YES" answer, when considering ONLY the questions in Step 3 that you judged as RELEVANT? If you do NOT AGREE, could you please provide a suggestion under 'Comments'?". Organize the comments of the participants by category.

- Participant P23: "Only because of the latter."
- Participant P24: "Again Q 3a and b seem more important than 1a-c."
- Participant P35: "I believe that updating is a means to improve the quality."
- Participant P43: "The problem with these questions is that they are not possible to answer without performing the review. You do not know whether the results will change until you do the review."
- Participant P55: "Again, I think this reduces a complicated uncertain situation to triviality."
- Participant P58: "A bit strange questions, although relevant. Sometimes you will not know whether more studies will change the conclusion when planning/deciding on whether doing an update or not. What is here a change in conclusion? Is even stronger evidence in favor of a relationship a change in conclusion? Updating a SLR that strengthen the previous finding may be worthwhile. PS: In the original decision framework there is a "maybe". I think that maybe makes meaning."
- Participant P62: "Again, balancing is key. We are far from ideal in SE to have fully SLRs. That's why I am confused with this classification. For instance, Rapid Reviews can be include here?"